

Determination and quantification of piroxicam in tablets by RP-HPLC

M. Saeed Arayne^{a*}, Najma Sultana^b and Farhan Ahmed Siddiqui^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Karachi, Karachi-75270, Pakistan

E-mail : arayne@gawab.com Fax : 92-21-4812699 & 9243173

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Karachi, Karachi, Pakistan

Manuscript received 16 November 2004, revised 5 April 2005, accepted 20 June 2005

A simple and rapid high-performance liquid chromatographic (HPLC) method for the determination and quantification of piroxicam has been developed and validated; meloxicam was used as internal standard. Methanol/water (70 : 30, v/v) was used as mobile phase, with flow rate 2 ml/min. pH was adjusted to 2.6 with phosphoric acid. UV detection was performed at 230 nm. Recovery of piroxicam (in Feldene Flash 20 mg tablets) was from 99.49 to 100.29%.

Piroxicam is 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-*N*-(pyridine-2-yl)-2*H*-1,2-benzothiazine-3-carboxamide-1,1-dioxide having molecular formula C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₄S, molecular weight 331.4 having following structure.

Piroxicam is also a non-steroidal antiinflammatory drug used in musculoskeletal and joint disorders, such as ankylosing spondylitis, osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, in soft tissue disorders, and in acute gout¹⁻⁴.

There are number of methods reported in the literature for the determination of piroxicam by HPLC⁵⁻⁹. Quantification of piroxicam in human plasma by HPLC with on and off-line solid phase extraction was reported by Yritia *et al.*¹⁰. HPLC determination with amperometric detection of piroxicam in human plasma and tissues was reported by de Jager *et al.*¹¹. LC determination of piroxicam in serum was reported by Fraser *et al.*¹². The present work describes a simple reverse phase HPLC method for the determination of piroxicam from reference materials, bulk raw materials and dosage formulations.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation the best separation of these

two compounds was achieved using a μ -Bondapak 125 A C18 (10 μ m) column. Using other type of column under the same experimental condition, the separation lasted about 28 min. For the determination of piroxicam and good resolution with internal standard the best results were obtained using methanol/water (70 : 30, v/v) mobile phase. The lower percentage of methanol in mobile phase results in peak tailing of both components and long analysis duration while higher percentage of methanol in mobile phase results very little analysis duration. Optimal retention times (piroxicam – 2.3 min and meloxicam – 3.3 min) were achieved when the pH of mobile phase was adjusted to 2.6 with 85% phosphoric acid. Small changes in pH of the mobile phase had a great influence to the chromatographic behavior of these substances. The higher pH of the mobile phase also results in peak tailing and at lower pH retention time of piroxicam and internal standard (meloxicam) is extremely long.

The accuracy of the method was evaluated by analyzing independently prepared solutions of piroxicam and meloxicam. The recovery data expressed in Table 1 shows that the method is accurate for determination and quantification of piroxicam.

The precision of the method was investigated with respect to repeatability. For intra-day precision, six concentrations of each compound were analyzed on the same day. Each concentration of sample was injected four times. Data of inter and intra day variation is summarized in Table 2. Generally acceptable repeatability of the results with in one day and day-to-day was observed. Data of the relative retention times obtained in a series of four consecutive injections also showed acceptable repeatability

Table 1. Recovery of piroxicam in reference drug and dosage form

Conc. (ppm) injected	Reference drug			Dosage form		
	Peak area	Found	% Recovery	Peak area	Found	% Recovery
0.5	9392	0.499	99.90	8676	0.504	100.08
1.0	18752	0.997	99.72	17324	0.999	99.92
1.5	28166	1.497	99.86	25961	1.497	99.82
2.0	37649	2.002	100.11	34779	2.006	100.29
2.5	47144	2.507	100.28	43123	2.487	99.49
3.0	56410	3.000	100.00	52095	3.004	100.15

Dosage form = Feldene Flash (Pfizer) 20 mg tablets.

Table 2. Intra and inter day variations in the analysis of piroxicam

Drug injected	Time	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	(+)S.D	RSD	Mean
5 ng	8:00	9363.00	8123.00	11279.00	8642.00	1381.79	0.15	9351.75
	11:00	9379.00	8149.00	11423.00	8696.00	1432.14	0.15	9411.75
	02:00	9409.00	8173.00	11467.00	8659.00	1451.93	0.15	9427.00
	05:00	9419.00	8136.00	11293.00	8709.00	1373.38	0.15	9389.25
10 ng	8:00	18832.00	16097.00	22933.00	17298.00	2980.19	0.16	18790.00
	11:00	18649.00	16277.00	22949.00	17270.00	2940.67	0.16	18786.25
	02:00	18723.00	16139.00	22629.00	17342.00	2818.99	0.15	18708.25
	05:00	18806.00	16240.00	22777.00	17386.00	2850.12	0.15	18802.25
15 ng	8:00	28236.00	24338.00	34433.00	25896.00	4437.43	0.16	28225.75
	11:00	28097.00	24475.00	34297.00	25949.00	4325.37	0.15	28204.50
	02:00	28129.00	24297.00	34338.00	26017.00	4384.78	0.16	28195.25
	05:00	28203.00	24430.00	34216.00	25983.00	4294.18	0.15	28208.00
20 ng	8:00	37732.00	32372.00	45686.00	34811.00	5787.95	0.15	37650.25
	11:00	37647.00	32493.00	45729.00	34729.00	5784.96	0.15	37649.50
	02:00	37620.00	32447.00	45837.00	34784.00	5839.84	0.16	37672.00
	05:00	37598.00	32578.00	45673.00	34830.00	5716.85	0.15	37669.75
25 ng	8:00	47162.00	40933.00	56817.00	42982.00	7055.72	0.15	46973.50
	11:00	47243.00	40876.00	56834.00	42956.00	7085.71	0.15	46977.25
	02:00	47092.00	40693.00	56807.00	42885.00	7137.43	0.15	46869.25
	05:00	47080.00	40719.00	57202.00	43672.00	7176.36	0.15	47168.25
30 ng	8:00	56493.00	48697.00	68358.00	52130.00	8574.57	0.15	56419.50
	11:00	56389.00	48927.00	68848.00	52109.00	8738.76	0.15	56568.25
	02:00	56443.00	48963.00	68524.00	52047.00	8587.11	0.15	56494.25
	05:00	56317.00	48861.00	68809.00	52096.00	8742.48	0.15	56520.75

when analyzed not only on the same day but also on four consecutive days. Recovery and regression characteristics of proposed method are given in Table 3.

System suitability of the method was evaluated by analyzing the symmetry of the piroxicam and meloxicam peaks (symmetry factor), theoretical plates of the column, resolution between the peaks of piroxicam and meloxicam, mass distribution ratio (capacity factor) and

relative retention. The specificity of the method was evaluated to ensure separation of piroxicam and meloxicam. The specificity of the method was demonstrated by assaying a sample of piroxicam and meloxicam. The method demonstrated clear resolution between piroxicam and internal standard (meloxicam). A typical chromatogram showing separation of piroxicam and meloxicam is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 3. Recovery and regression characteristics of proposed method

Concentration ($\mu\text{g-ml}$) injected	Recovered concentration			
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4
0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00
1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50
2.00	2.00	1.99	2.00	2.01
2.50	2.51	2.51	2.49	2.49
3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Correlation coefficient (R)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999
Standard error of estimate	0.0034	0.0045	0.0051	0.0074
Intercept	-0.0029	-0.0046	-0.0016	-0.0002
P value	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Standard error of estimate	0.0034	0.0045	0.0051	0.0074
Slope	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Fig. 1. A typical chromatogram of piroxicam and meloxicam (internal standard). Piroxicam = 2.6 min; internal standard = 3.3 min.

The limit of quantitation of developed method was found 500 ng/ml, while the detection limit was found 200 ng/ml. Ruggedness of this method was evaluated in two different Labs with two different instruments of the same model and make.

Experimental

Material and reagents : Samples of piroxicam and meloxicam were a kind gift from AGP (Private) Limited. Feldene Flash 20 mg tablets were purchased from market. HPLC grade methanol and phosphoric acid were obtained from Merck, Germany. The mobile phase and solutions were prepared in deionized double distilled water. Stock solutions of the compounds were prepared in methanol. Fresh working solutions were prepared daily.

All solution were filtered (0.45 μm) and degassed by sonicator.

Apparatus : The HPLC systems used in both Labs were identical and were LC-10 AT VP Shimadzu pump, SPD-10AV VP Shimadzu UV visible detector, a μ -Bondapak 125 A C18 10 cm column (particle size 10 μm) was used for separation. The chromatographic and integrated data were recorded using a CBM-102 communication Bus Module Shimadzu.

Chromatographic conditions : The mobile phase was methanol/water (70 : 30). The pH of this mobile phase was adjusted to 2.6 with phosphoric acid (85%). Prior to delivering into the system it was filtered through 0.45 μm filter and degassed using a sonicator. The analysis was carried out under isocratic conditions using a flow rate 2.0 ml/min at room temperature. Chromatograms were recorded at 230 nm using a detector SPD-10AV VP Shimadzu UV visible. The samples were introduced by injector with a 10- μl iter sample loop.

Analytical procedure : 10 mg piroxicam and 10 mg of meloxicam were dissolved in methanol in 100 ml volumetric flask separately and made up the volume (stock solution 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Aliquots were appropriately diluted. Ten tablets of Feldene Flash 20 mg were weighed to obtain the average tablets weight, and were then powdered. Powdered tablets were mixed with 100 ml methanol containing 10 mg of piroxicam. This mixture was allowed to stand for 1 h with intermittent sonication to ensure complete solubility of the drug (stock solution). This stock solution was filtered and this clear filtrate was diluted to desire concentrations. 10 μl iter volume of each sample was injected and chromatographed under above conditions.

Conclusion : A rapid, precise, accurate, low cost and least time consuming RP-HPLC method for the qualitative and quantitative analysis, determination and quantification of piroxicam and meloxicam in raw materials, in all dosages formulations has been successfully developed.

The proposed RP-HPLC method enables simultaneous determination of piroxicam and meloxicam because of good separation and resolution of the chromatographic peaks. The obtained results are in a good agreement with the declared contents of dosage formulations. Results are accurate and precise and are confirmed by the statistical parameters. Reliability, rapidness, simplicity, sensitivity, economical nature, good recovery and precision of this HPLC method give it advantage over to the other reported HPLC methods for determination of piroxicam and meloxicam.

References

1. The Merck Index, "An Encyclopedia of Chemical, Drugs and Biologicals", 13th ed., Merck Research Laboratories, Division of Merck & Co Inc., Whitehouse Station, NJ, 2001, pp. 1346.
2. Martindale, The extra pharmacopoeia, 31st ed., copyright 1996. Published by the Royal Pharmaceutical Society of Great Britain, 1 Lambeth High Street, London SE 17 Jn England, pp. 91-92.
3. United State Pharmacopoeia 2004, copyright 2003. The United State Pharmacopeial Convention, Inc. 12601 Twinbrook Parkway, Rockville, MD 20852, pp. 1499, 2776.
4. British Pharmacopoeia 2003, Crown copyright 2003. Published by The Stationary office under licence from the controller of Her Majesty's stationary office for the Department of Health on behalf of the Health Ministers, pp. 1501-02.
5. A. Avgerinos, S. Axarlis, J. Dragatsist, T. Karidas and S. Malamataris, *J. Chromatogr. B : Biomed. Appl.*, 1995, **673**, 142.
6. L. Ednol, F. Bressolle, B. Combe and M. Galtier, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1995, **13**, 785.
7. M. T. Maya, J. P. Pais and J. A. Morais, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1995, **13**, 319.
8. M. G. Donato, W. Baeyens, W. van den Bossche and P. Sandra, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1994, **12**, 21.
9. M. Amanlou and A. R. Dehpour, *J. Chromatogr. B : Biomed. Sci. Appl.*, 1997, **696**, 317.
10. M. Yritia, P. Parra, J. M. Fernandez and J. M. Barbanoj, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1999, **846**, 199.
11. A. D. de Jager, H. Elis, H. K. Hundt, K. J. Swart and A. F. Hundt, *J. Chromatogr. B : Biomed. Sci. Appl.*, 1999, **729**, 183.
12. A. D. Fraser and J. F. Woodbury, *Ther. Drug Monit.*, 1983, **5**, 239.